

Supplementary Figures

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This section provides additional supplementary figures that are largely in parallel with those presented in the main article, apart for different publication years. Supplementary Figures 1 and 2 present the top 100 universities in total open access, open access (gold) publishing and repository-mediated (green) open access, for the publication years 2016 and 2018, respectively. These are produced analogously to Figure 1 of the main text.

Supplementary Figures 3 to 5 are figures based on the complete list of universities (i.e., without filtering on margin of error). These represent the open access performances across different countries for the years 2016, 2017 and 2018. In parallel, Supplementary Figures 6 to 8 gives the overviews as per region.

Supplementary Figure 9 is an extended version of Figure 3 of the main text and presents corresponding time-stamped figures from 2007 to 2018. Supplementary Figure 10 provides additional information to Figure 4 of the main text.

Supplementary Figure 1: Top 100 universities in terms of performance in Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA for 2016

Supplementary Figure 2: Top 100 universities in terms of performance in Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA for 2018

Supplementary Figure 3: Percentages of institutional Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA (left to right) grouped by countries for 2017

Supplementary Figure 4: Percentages of institutional Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA (left to right) grouped by countries for 2016

Supplementary Figure 5: Percentages of institutional Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA (left to right) grouped by countries for 2018

Supplementary Figure 6: Percentages of institutional Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA (left to right) grouped by regions for 2017

Supplementary Figure 7: Percentages of institutional Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA (left to right) grouped by regions for 2018

Supplementary Figure 8: Percentages of institutional Total OA, Gold OA and Green OA (left to right) grouped by regions for 2016

Supplementary Figure 9: Open access publishing vs repository-mediated open access by institution from 2007-2018

Supplementary Figure 10: Additional figures for monitoring the effect of policy interventions for selected groups of universities.

